

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Nelson**FIRST NAME:** Junior Céranor**PROGRAM CODE:** MDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Laurent Cleenewerck

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)
The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord version 16.25 on macOS Mojave)

THE COGNITION OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The collection of readings assembled for the first period of EUCLID University provides a detailed overview of the basics of academic writing. This pack assists in pointing out the mistakes made in writing academic papers. The correct format of writing these papers has been shown in the overview. By conducting a thorough analysis of the document, I have gained significant knowledge on correcting my mistakes in writing academic papers. Not very well paged, the document has also provided me the scope of following the actual format which can enhance the quality of my academic writings. The contents can be useful for anyone who is looking forward to writing academic papers. I think the methodology used is adequate and practical to magnify the skills of students in writing a good essay. The information about the correct format of the referencing, paraphrasing and styles of writing provided, reflect basic rules will be useful for my current studies as well as my future ones.

2) CONTENTS OF THE COURSEPACK

The document begins with an attractive opening, by asking the question, “what does a good essay need?” this introduction Captures the essential rules to write a good essay. In addition, the coursepack emphasizes on how to plan and develop an essay. the coursepack describes the importance of avoiding plagiarism and using citations properly in order to improve the quality of writing with some key details. Therefore, the basics of writing academic papers have been provided along with the steps that the writers should follow. Furthermore, the content demonstrates that with proper research, it is possible to construct an essay in a manner which can help the writers to express their perspective efficiently (Graham & Harris, 2014). The process of drafting and editing of the contents of the essay has been highlighted with proper points that help to acquire important knowledge.

Additionally, the study material supplied by EUCLID also provided some examples of references styles that can be used in essays. It aptly described, the process of citation and also explains when to cite and when not to. For instance, it states you must acknowledge the author/s when you use their ideas rather than your own words or thoughts, on the other hand, you do not need to cite if it's common knowledge (EUCLID 2019, 30).

To sum up the contents illustrates the importance of correct citation and use of references and mostly insist on the prevention of plagiarism. This information can be regarded as significant in terms of identifying which lines to cite, how to do it properly.

a) Overview on the format of referencing

Previously, I had knowledge about basic referencing styles such as APA (American Psychological Association) and Harvard, however; I faced problems while using other styles such as Chicago, Vancouver and others. I have mostly worked on APA (American Psychological Association) style papers and the process of using the Turabian style papers has been relatively unknown for me. However; after going through the contents of this document, I have now able with more confidence using this format.

According to EUCLID University Two types of referencing have been preferred for conducting the academic works. While most of the academic papers of EUCLID are required to be written in the format of Chicago referencing style while some limited response papers can be also written in the style of APA (American Psychological Association) referencing. Turabian referencing is similar to the Chicago however; this is used for the student version and is much shorter than that of Chicago referencing (Is turabian style the same as Chicago Style, 2015) therefore; this educational material aptly described the methods by which the footnotes and bibliography are created in the Chicago style of referencing.

b) Overview provided on the use of American and British English

Through this collection of readings, I learned important knowledge about the differences between American and British English. With some key details it was showed how the American English is used more than British English due to a number of factors. Some of these factors that have been identified in the document include the greater population, enormity of higher education and a greater number of the publishing firms in the country makes the use of American English more than the British English in the academic writing.

I noticed some differences made with the given examples of some words which have same pronunciation, however; have different spellings for example “gaol” and “jail.” The study also showed the different meanings of similar words which differ the two types of English for example: “GB trousers’ = US ‘pants’; US ‘pants’ = GB ‘underwear pants.’” With this proper clarification of the differences in these popular languages of academic

writing, I will definitely use the terms and words confidently in my academic papers in the future.

“American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological and cultural influence worldwide” (EUCLID 2019, 54)

Through this quote, it has been possible to understand the dominance of American English in the context of academic writing. I have also learned the information about the method by which the quotations and commas differ in these two types of English. For example, in a quotation sentence the British will place the period after the quotation mark (".") while the American will place it before ("."). With proper examples and all the differences, this textbook has been relevant in terms of using the right way or spellings while using any of these two types of English.

i) *Sentence construction and use of words in academic papers*

After going through the coursepack, I was able to identify and prevent such errors in my writing papers as I'm not a native English speaking, I never really pay attention with the employ of some simple rules. In many of the academic papers, I used to make mistakes regarding the use of proper grammars and words which are relevant to the academic styles of writing. I was more meticulous after reading this document.

These details will be able to increase the quality of my writings which would be apt with the standard of writing that is required to be followed. Through the contents provided in the coursepack, relevant knowledge about the construction of the sentences and use of appropriate words or grammars in the academic papers has been identified. With the examples that have been shown in the sections, I learned relevant skills about the differences in the use of words in academic writing and other types of writings. A known fact about academic writing, in this style of writing more formal words and sentences are required to be used rather than using any type words which are informal, or which have casual representation (Badenhorst, McLeod, & Toll 2018, 197-212) Therefore; I was able to identify relevant formal words and sentences which are required to be used instead of using any informal words. To sum up this section of the collection of reading assembled, the overall description that has been provided has been explained in simple languages and with a number of examples, which helps the readers to understand and tame the use of two popular styles of English with efficiency.

ii) *Simplification of the sentences in academic writing*

While writing report and thesis papers, I made many mistakes on the construction of sentences. Some of the sentences were long and some had issues regarding quality. The guidelines that have been presented in the EUCLID document, allow me to identify the standard rules of writing academic reports and thesis papers. With these guidelines, this packet provided a brief overview of the significant rules furthermore the personal style of writing is mostly based on using contractions which are strictly prohibited in the academic writings (Fang & Park, 2019). This has been efficiently discussed in the packet with the

help of relevant examples such as “don’t” better to write “do not” or aren’t, better to write “are not,” Writing short, clear sentences were advised.

“Write clearly. That's easier said than done, and hard to make operational. But you can make a first step by writing short sentences, avoiding page-long paragraphs, and being careful to signal transitions.” (EUCLID 2019, 43)

This quote states about one of the instructions that needs to be followed in the process of writing academic papers. Following the instructions provided in this educational material, we can ameliorate the quality of the sentences and the grammar significantly. Therefore; the brief demonstration of these reminders has been provided efficiently in terms of points to help the viewers understand those in a better way.

3) CONCLUSION

This collection of educational material has helped in learning about the basic rules that are required to be followed in the process of writing academic papers. The words and sentences that have been used in this document are simple to understand with the sections divided. Each of the rules has been explained with the help of relevant examples which helped in understanding the contents efficiently and without much challenges.

Being a graduate in the field of science, I would be able to make use of these rules during the course in the EUCLID University. Although I do have experiences in writing academic papers, however; with the help of this coursepack, I have further gained the knowledge which can increase the quality of the papers which I would write during the course in the University. The issues of writing that have been identified through the paper would be highly useful in terms of being aware of the construction of sentences and grammars in the academic papers. The issues of plagiarism can be also prevented significantly due to the knowledge that has been received about citations and quotes. This knowledge that the paper has provided can be useful for all the students who need to write their academic papers and shine in their own academic field in the future.

REFERENCES

Badenhorst, McLeod, and Haley Toll. 2018. *Beyond Words: Academic Writing Identities and Imaginative (Artistic) Selves*.

EUCLID University, 2019. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, Retrieved from: <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>.

Fang and Park, 2019. Use of Academic Language in Informational Writing, *Reading and Writing*.

Graham and Harris. 2014. Conducting High Quality Writing Intervention Research: Twelve Recommendations,” *Journal of Writing Research* 6.

“Is Turabian Style the Same as Chicago Style?” *CMOS Shop Talk*, February 3, 2015, accessed June 7, 2019, <http://cmosshoptalk.com/2015/02/03/for-students-is-turabian-style-the-same-as-chicago-style/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.